

UCD School of Earth Sciences
Scoil na nDomhaneolaíochtaí UCD

CAGEO
CENTRE FOR
APPLIED GEOPHYSICS
AND
DATA INTEGRATION

Petrophysics metadata statement

Study area: Limerick Basin, Ireland

Drill hole: TC-2638-019

TITLE

Chargeability, Compressional Velocity (V_p), Density, Galvanic Electric Resistivity, Gamma Ray Spectrometry (K, Th, U), Inductive Electric Conductivity, Magnetic Susceptibility, Portable X-Ray Fluorescence (pXRF), and Shear Velocity (V_s) of the Drillhole TC-2638-019 in Limerick Basin, Ireland.

KEYWORDS

Petrophysics; physical properties; basalt; diatremes; Irish Orefield; mineral exploration; geothermal

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DATA COLLECTION

University College Dublin (UCD) Petrophysics Laboratory

CUSTODIAN

Center for Applied Geophysics and Data Integration (CAGEO)

JURISDICTION

Ireland

ABSTRACT

This report contains the metadata statement of the petrophysical data of drill hole TC-2638-019 acquired by researchers of the CAGEO Research Group at the UCD Petrophysics Laboratory. The database is comprised of the following physical properties:

Chargeability	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Compressional Velocity (Vp)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Density	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Galvanic Electric Resistivity	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Gamma Ray Spectrometry (K, Th, U)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Inductive Electric Conductivity	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Magnetic Susceptibility	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Portable X-Ray Fluorescence (pXRF)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Shear Velocity (Vs)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		<input type="checkbox"/>

GEOGRAPHIC INFORMATION

Projection: ITM

Datum: IRENET95

Easting: 564214.2469

Northing: 648157.692

Collar elevation: 109

Length: 563.4

Azimuth: 0

Dip: 90

Diameter: NQ

TOTAL NUMBER OF SAMPLES

26

DESCRIPTION

The core was sampled approximately every 20 meters with additional samples in areas of specific geological variations. The samples are approximately 10 cm in length, have flat ends and unique sample IDs.

This drill hole intersects the following geological units: Knockroe Volcanics Formation

Important geological features are: basalts, diatremes, altered basalts

All the measurements were taken following the procedures described in Melo et al (2025). Content of the database:

Tab	Description
hole_id	Drillhole ID
sample_id	Sample ID (e.g., from the drill hole or field campaign)
depth_from	Depth location of the sample in the drillhole (top of sample)
depth_to	Depth location of the sample in the drillhole (bottom of sample)
den	Density (g/cm ³)
sus *	Magnetic susceptibility (10 ⁻³ SI)
cond *	Inductive electric conductivity (S/m)
v_p	Compressional Velocity (m/s)
v_s	Shear Velocity (m/s)
ip_res	Chargeability (mV/V) and Galvanic electric resistivity (Ohm.m)
gamma	Gamma Ray Spectrometry K (%)
	Gamma Ray Spectrometry U (ppm)
	Gamma Ray Spectrometry Th (ppm)
xrf *	Portable X-Ray Fluorescence (ppm)
cal	Quality control measurements taken every 10 samples

* Parameters are given as maximum (max), minimum (min), mean (mean), and standard deviation (std).

CHANGES SINCE THE PREVIOUS VERSION

None

FORMATS

Digital	Description
DIGITAL	PDF file for metadata
DIGITAL	Microsoft Excel spreadsheet for the database

LICENSE FOR THE REPORT AND ASSOCIATED DATABASE

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CONTACT ORGANIZATION

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REFERENCES

Melo A., Susin V., Chakraborti P., and Wei N. 2025. *Methodology for Measuring Chargeability, Compressional Velocity (Vp), Density, Galvanic Electric Resistivity, Gamma Ray Spectrometry (K, Th, U), Inductive Electric Conductivity, Magnetic Susceptibility, Portable X-Ray Fluorescence (XRF), and Shear Velocity (Vs) of Drill Core Rock Samples at the UCD Petrophysics Laboratory.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16903342>.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

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